
The Role of Technology Use in Moderating the Influence of Social Capital and Work Environment on Teacher Performance

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ABSTRACT: Many things are indicated as the driving force in improving performance, and the success of a graduate at the high school level cannot be separated from an educator (teacher). So this research aims to determine the moderating influence of the use of technology in encouraging performance between social capital and the work environment on teacher performance. This research uses a quantitative descriptive approach with primary and secondary data sources. The research population was all teachers in high schools in Sekotong sub-district, West Lombok, namely 91 teachers. Determination of samples using purposive sampling so that 91 teacher informants were obtained. The research instrument used a questionnaire distributed using Google Form. Data analysis method using path analysis and with SmartPLS 4.0 as a processing tool. The results of this research are that social capital is proven to have no significant effect on teacher performance, meaning that a wide and dense network of relationships does not have an effect on increasing teacher performance for high school/vocational school level teachers in Cendi Manik Village, Sekotong District, West Lombok Regency, West Nusa Tenggara. Meanwhile, the work environment has been proven to have a significant positive effect on teacher performance. This means that the better the work environment, the better the teacher performance will be at the High School teachers in Cendi Manik Village, Sekotong District, West Lombok Regency, West Nusa Tenggara. Then technology is not proven to moderate social capital and the work environment on teacher performance. This means that technology must be balanced with other things to support it, for example balancing knowledge with training and updating knowledge.

KEYWORDS: Social Capital, Work Environment, Use of Technology and Teacher Performance

1. INTRODUCTION

Currently, education in Indonesia is regulated through Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System.

Education in Indonesia is divided into three main channels, namely formal, non-formal and informal. Education is also divided into four levels, namely early childhood, primary, secondary and tertiary. Currently, the education system in Indonesia can be said to be very ineffective, the system in this country forces its students to become multi-talented people, forcing students to master all subjects at school, even though each student has their own strengths and weaknesses.

The education that should be implemented in this country is to focus on the talents within students. For example, at the elementary and middle school levels, the focus is used to find the identity or talents of each student, explore and find out what fields the students like, then teach or tell what things each student must learn to achieve their dreams in that field. Interested. Furthermore, at the high school/equivalent level, each student can focus on the field of their respective talents, given subjects that are related to or appropriate to their field, subjects that students will need after graduating from school. High school level or equivalent is an environment where a teenager will begin the stage of searching for identity and this stage is a release between the dependent and independent stages. The performance of a teacher at the high school level is more focused on learning, being able to be flexible in giving assignments at any time, carrying out teaching and learning activities at any time by agreement with the students.

The operation of the above educational units is supported by 921 preschool tutors/teachers, 2,590 elementary school teachers, 692 middle school teachers and 391 high school (SMA) teachers and 228 vocational school (SMK) teachers. From these figures, based on the results of the analysis of teacher needs, it can be explained that currently West Lombok Regency still lacks 817 teachers for elementary schools, 113 for middle schools, 111 for high schools (SMA) and 361 for vocational schools(SMK). Likewise, the provision of other learning facilities is still inadequate, including: classrooms, laboratory rooms, library rooms, multipurpose rooms and other practical rooms. To improve quality, it is also still necessary to provide books, teaching aids and training for teaching staff whose qualifications are currently not yet graduate level; 53.34% elementary school teachers, 12.66%

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middle school teachers, 6.5% high school (SMA) teachers and 16.4% vocational school (SMK) teachers. The problem of teacher shortages makes teacher performance less than optimal. So a special strategy is needed to overcome this.

Table 1. Number of Teachers in Cendi Manik Village, Sekotong District, West Lombok Regency 2018-2022

No	Region	Amount	Employment status	Teaching Extras
1.	Sekotong ISLAMIC HIGH SCHOOL	23 People	12 Permanent Teachers and staff 5 non-permanent Teacher 6 honorary Teachers	Extracurricular Supervisor; Head of Laboratory; Head of Library
2.	Sekotong 1 st Vocational School	32 People	22 honorary Teachers 5 Permanent Teachers/Staff 5 non-permanent Teachers/Staff	Deputy Head of Curriculum; Deputy Head of Facility; Deputy Head of Student Affairs; Deputy Head of Public Relations
3.	Sekotong I High School	36 people	16 Permanent Teachers/Staff 15 honorary Teachers 5 non-permanent Teachers/Staff	Head of Laboratory; Picket Teacher; Head of Library; Girl Scout Leader

Source: SMA/SMK schools in West Lombok 2024

Based on Table 1 above, it can be seen that secondary level education in Cendi Manik Village, Sekotong District, West Lombok Regency is still very short of teachers, with only 48 people being permanent teachers in the school environment, the rest are still honorary, which of course will result in many adaptation discrepancies. Teaching and impact on teaching or student achievement. Achieving teacher performance cannot be separated from many factors. In its development, human resource management for educators still has many obstacles.

Teacher performance is an indicator that is usually used to measure the success of a business in achieving predetermined goals and targets (Sumbodo et al., 2019; Sparrow, 2015), or the ability of all stakeholder components to meet community satisfaction. Good performance can be influenced by many factors such as networks (social capital) (Norayati et al, 2022; Zhang et al, 2021), and also influenced by the work environment (Afriyani et al, 2018; Abdullah, 2020; Wei, 2018; Giorgi et al, 2020), or technology (Dunaetz, Jaiswal et al, 2022). Because the work environment and social capital without the support of infrastructure (technology), both cannot produce high results of output (Jaiswal et al, 2022); Setini et al. (2021). The work environment at the high school/equivalent level in Cendi Manik Village, Sekotong District, West Lombok Regency, West Nusa Tenggara still shows a lack of a conducive work environment, if seen from the infrastructure, for example, rooms that are still not conducive to studying, there is no LCD media. Projectors for presenting presentations, the absence of a lab as a medium for teaching science and also the atmosphere in the study room which is not sufficiently ventilated. Results of a pre-survey conducted in April 2022 at 10 am on 20 teachers who were interviewed, evidence of the interviews is attached in the attachment.

Several studies regarding the influence of social capital and the work environment on teacher performance show mixed results. Inconsistencies in previous research were found in research by Yasa (2018); Setini et al. (2020), Putra, et al (2020), Giatari, et al (2019), which found that social capital and the work environment had a significant positive effect on performance. Meanwhile, Iswari et al, (2019), Kokoroko & Sanda, (2019), Inegbedion et al, (2019), Robelski, et al, (2019), obtaining social capital results does not have a significant effect on the work success of teachers/staff. Research by Wakhyuni (2018), Inegbedion et al (2018), Johari, et al (2019), Novianti & Roz (2020). Wang, et al (2019) and Holland, et al (2019) found that social capital had a negative effect on performance. Research by Trihudyatmanto and Purwanto (2018), Budiharso & Tarman (2020), and Geiger & Pivovarov (2018) found that the work environment had no significant effect on employee performance. Meanwhile, Badrianto & Ekhsan (2020), Ramli (2019) and Parashakti, et al (2020) found that the work environment had a negative effect on employee performance. According to Saris, et al (2009), misspecification of a research model can result in differences in research results or inconclusive results. In general, positive, negative or neutral results from research are due to the absence of moderating variables or moderating variables on the relationship between workload and work environment on employee performance. In this research, to improve teacher performance, technology variables were used. This is proven because competition affects the performance of all sectors, so education must always be able to keep up with the times (Ferreira et al, 2020). The importance of supporting resources practices can be a driving force in increasing the acceleration of work in an organization that is always results-oriented and allows companies to be more effective in completing work and provide more optimal service to the community (Saedi et al., 2019). This will have an impact on teacher performance in accordance with research (Haseeb et al, 2019), (Andriani et al, 2018), and (Parker and Grote, 2022) which states that technology has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

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Technology can be applied well if it is based on self-will or self-efficacy. Self-efficacy plays an important role in many parts of human life, including building life systems and shaping individual behavior and also has a positive influence on employee activities, which in turn has the potential to help maintain company performance or police performance (Dirani, et al, 2020). Besides that, self-efficacy, which is self-image in the form of perseverance and self-confidence in carrying out tasks, can function as an explanatory variable or driver of success in the police work environment (Dien and Joeliaty, 2022; Tynan, et al, 2020). Based on the description above, the research title used in this study is "THE ROLE OF TECHNOLOGY USE IN MODERATE THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL CAPITAL AND WORK ENVIRONMENT ON TEACHER PERFORMANCE (Study at High School/Equivalent in Cendi Manik Village, Sekotong District, West Lombok Regency, West Nusa Tenggara)".

2. LIBRARY REVIEW

2.1 Resource Based Theory

Resource Based Theory or what is commonly called as well Resource Based View is one of the basic theories that supports social capital. This theory believes that a company will achieve excellence if it has superior resources (Kholik & Laeli, 2020). Resource Based Theory is a method for analyzing and identifying the strategic advantages of a company based on a review of the combination of assets, skills, capabilities and intangible assets that are special to an organization/company.

Birger Wenerfelt (1984) explains that according to the view Resource Based Theory Organizations will excel in business competition and obtain good teacher performance by owning, controlling and utilizing important strategic assets (tangible assets and intangible assets). Sirojudin, & Nazaruddin (2014) said a potential strategy to improve organizational performance is to combine tangible assets and intangible assets.

According to this theory, the benefits of networking are positive outcomes between company resources and performance measurements. Networks are intangible resources that are conveyed in this theory to be obtained from the ability to have all the characteristics of strategic knowledge. While most intangible assets do not qualify as strategic assets, intellectual capital is generally considered an important strategic asset whose possession means special and valuable knowledge is possessed by the company.

Resource based theory discusses how companies can achieve competitive advantage by developing and analyzing the resources they have, highlighting the superiority of knowledge or an economy that relies on intangible assets. Wernerfelt (1984) explains that according to the Resource-Based Theory view, companies will increasingly excel in business competition and obtain good teacher performance by owning, controlling and utilizing important strategic assets (tangible and intangible assets). Sirojudin, & Nazaruddin (2014), stated that a potential strategy to improve company performance is to combine tangible assets and intangible assets.

According to (Sudargini, 2021), the main goal of network-based performance is to create added value. To be able to create added value, an appropriate measure of physical capital is needed in the form of network strength represented by employees with all their inherent potential and abilities. Based on approach Resource-Based Theory It can be concluded that the resources owned by the company influence organizational performance which will ultimately increase company value. One of the resources that a company has from the intangible assets disclosed is social capital.

2.2 Relationship between Variables

2.2.1 The Influence of Social Capital on Teacher Performance

Investigations conducted on teacher's show that social capital influences a teacher in carrying out teaching practices. However, social capital has two types of messages for certain groups of people, namely those with strong ties such as family and friends or those with weak ties such as acquaintances leading consumers to post and share teaching pattern messages. It should be noted that both types of messages provide information on the quality of teaching information, services and experiences and can influence instructors' intentions and behavior (Johnson, 2012). Positive statements on online communication can increase teachers' positive attitudes towards teaching patterns, service to students, and increase students' interest in learning. Conversely, negative social capital can cause serious and sometimes even irreversible damage to education (Sapta et al., 2020). Communication messages on the network can reduce the possibility of uncertainty for students and teachers when carrying out the teaching and learning process, so that teacher performance can be more effective.

Several previous studies are in line with those expressed by Johnson (2012) Collie *et al.* (2012); Kraft *et al.* (2016); Ingersoll *et al.* (2014) has a good and positive influence on improving performance. Apart from that, Simbula et al (2011) explained that social capital can encourage students' interest in learning through online/digital media in Taiwan. Mishra (2020) researched 120 teachers in Japan to prove that social capital has a positive effect on learning intentions. Sibieta's (2018) research in New York, Los Angeles, and Chicago found that social capital as measured by usefulness, credibility, information quality, and professionalism effectively predicted the level of learning intention. Based on theory and several previous researchers, the following hypothesis was formulated:

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H1 : Social Capital has a positive and significant effect on Teacher Performance

2.2.2 The Influence of the Work Environment on Teacher Performance

The work environment is the conditions surrounding the teaching staff which have an influence on their work, both internal and external environments Abouelela (2022). The fulfillment of the internal and external environment creates a situation where a teaching staff feels comfortable and enjoys the workplace (Alamry, 2022). The work environment in schools that is able to support teacher productivity in their work includes; the existence of adequate teaching facilities, lighting, privacy of the work space, cleanliness, color selection, safety, good size and layout of the work space, and relationships between co-workers and superiors are important things to pay attention to in creating a pleasant working atmosphere (Dirsaet *al.*, 2022).

One of the teacher's duties is as an instructor who transfers knowledge. Apart from that, teachers are also educators who transfer values as well as mentors who provide direction and guide students in learning (Martin-Kerret *al.*, 2022). For this reason, the work environment in schools must be able to support the work of teachers. so that it can work well, comfortably and conductively, so that it will lead to high performance. From the previous description there is an implication that, if the work environment is not good the impact on teacher performance will be a decrease in teacher efficiency in completing their tasks, whereas if the work environment is good and supportive the impact on teacher performance will increase productivity in teaching and learning activities, and can create enthusiasm in completing tasks as a teacher (Bardaet *al.*, 2022). Based on theory and several previous researchers, the following hypothesis was formulated:

H2: The work environment has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance.

2.2.3 Technology in Moderating the Effect of Social Capital on Teacher Performance

In the findings of (Kearney & Garfield (2022), the use of technology as a learning medium will clearly make the teaching and learning process effective and efficient because it can make it easier for a teacher to obtain or convey information (message or content, material) for lessons, and can help increase student understanding. , presentation of more data/information. The role of technology in learning is to facilitate the formation of collaborative relationships and build meaning in a context that is easier to understand. In detail, technology can be directed at building collaborative communication networks between teachers, lecturers, students and learning resources. Technology used in education aims to facilitate learning, therefore all existing technology and the resulting educational technology products must be selected and built based on an analysis of the needs of a particular learning environment.

Previous research by (Putrid and Imaniyati, 2017) shows that the positive impact of information technology in the world of education is: the information needed will be faster and easier to access for educational purposes, innovation in learning is increasingly developing with the existence of e-learning innovation which makes the educational process easier, advances in information technology. By utilizing information technology, teachers can present more interesting material. For example, providing a clear and relevant context so that students gain a comprehensive understanding (Hughes, 2014). Technology becomes a bridge in conveying all information, making routine implementation easier if supported by a large community so that learning outcomes can be achieved (Liang and Akiba, 2017). Based on this explanation, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H3 : Technology is able to moderate the influence of Social Capital on Teacher Performance.

2.2.4 Technology in Moderating the Influence of the Work Environment on Teacher Performance

The work environment in the school environment is an atmosphere where teachers carry out daily teaching activities. A conducive work environment provides a sense of security and allows employees to work optimally, the presence of technology being a positive issue in the work environment can provide a barter of knowledge related to the teaching system implemented. The work environment in the high school environment in Cendi Manik Lombok, West Nusa Tenggara is actually already conducive to the learning performance achievements that have been achieved. The presence of technology, especially during the Covid era, will really help achieve a faster teaching and learning process. Previous research conducted by (Zeichner, 2014) obtained the result that there is an influence of technology on the relationship between the work environment and teacher performance through educational delivery technology that can be used as a learning development. Research (Simon & Johnson, 2015) conducted on education in China shows that technology accelerates learning so that the work environment becomes more productive. Based on this explanation, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H4: Technology is able to moderate the influence of the work environment on Teacher Performance.

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Figure 3.1 Research Rationale Framework
 Source: Pcessed by the author (2024)

3. METHOD

This research will be conducted at high school/equivalent School level in Cendi Manik Village, Sekotong District, West Lombok Regency, West Nusa Tenggara Province. This is based on the fact that secondary level education in West Lombok is still very short in the number of teachers, it can be seen that only 48 people are permanent teachers in the school environment, the rest are still honorary, which of course will result in many incompatibilities in teaching adaptation and have an impact on teaching or student achievement. Achieving teacher performance cannot be separated from many factors. In its development, human resource management for educators still has many obstacles. The population in this study were all teachers at High School/Equivalent School level in Cendi Manik Village, Sekotong District, West Lombok Regency, West Nusa Tenggara, totaling 91 consisting of permanent teachers, honorary teachers and non permanent teachers. According to Sugiyono (2014: 118), the saturated sampling technique is a sample determination technique when all members of the population are used as samples. Therefore, the author chose the sample using a saturated sampling technique because the population size was relatively small. So the sample used in this research was 91 people. Data collection will be carried out using a questionnaire, namely a data collection technique by giving a set of written statements to respondents for them to answer. The form of questionnaire used by researchers is a questionnaire with closed questions with alternative answers in the form of likert Scale. The analysis in this research is path analysis by using Partial Least Square (PLS), Where weight estimate is to obtain latent variable scores, path coefficient is to estimate the relationship between latent variables, and loading factor is to estimate the relationship between latent variables and their indicators.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Results

Respondent Characteristics

1. Characteristics of Respondents Based on Gender

Based on the research results, the characteristics of respondents based on gender are as shown in the following table:

Table 2. Characteristics of Respondents Based on Gender

No	Gender	Number of people	Percentage
1	Man	61	67,04
2	Woman	30	32,96
	Amount	91	100

Source: Respondent Primary Data (2024)

From Table 4.1, it can be seen that 61 respondents were male (67.04%), and 30 female respondents (32.96%). Based on these gender characteristics, it shows that the number of male respondents is greater than the number of female respondents. This data further confirms that the number of male teachers is greater than female.

2. Characteristics of Respondents Based on Age

Based on the research results, the characteristics of respondents based on age are as shown in the following table:

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Table 3. Characteristics of Respondents Based on Age

No.	Age (Years)	Amount	Percentage
1	< 30 years	7	7,69
2	31-35 tahun	15	17,46
3	36- 40 years old	41	44,91
4	41-50 years old	25	26,84
5	> 50 years	3	3,10
Amount		91	100

Source: Primary Data, Processed (2024)

From Table 3, it can be explained that respondents aged <30 years were 7 people (7.69%), 31-35 years were 15 people (17.46%), 36-40 years were 41 people (44.91%) , 41-50 years as many as 25 people (26.84%), and >50 years 3 people (3.10%). The characteristics of respondents based on age show that the number of 36-40 and 41-50 year olds is 66 people (71.75%), meaning that the respondents are of productive adult age and have experience in their fields so they can be expected to be more responsible, able to improve their achievements and more productive in carry out tasks.

3. Characteristics of Respondents Based on Years of Work

Based on the research results, the characteristics of respondents are based on length of service as shown in the following table:

Table 4. Characteristics of Respondents Based on Years of Work

No.	Working time	Number of people	Percentage
1	<5 years	39	40,01
2	6-10 years	25	24,62
3	10-15 years	31	26,58
4	>16 years	8	8,79
Amount		91	100

Source: Primary Data, Processed (2024)

From Table 4, it can be seen that respondents with a working period of <5 years were 39 people (40.01%), 6-10 years were 25 people (24.62%), 10-15 years were 31 people (26.58%).), and >16 years as many as 8 people (8.79%). Characteristics based on respondents' work experience show that as many as 64 people (69.99%) of respondents have worked more than 6-16 years, so they are expected to have sufficient experience, knowledge and skills in carrying out their duties as an educator.

4. Characteristics of Respondents Based on Position Level

Based on the research results, the characteristics of respondents based on group level are as shown in the following table:

Table 5. Characteristics of Respondents Based on Position Level

No.	Group	Number of people	Percentage
1	Headmaster	3	3,96
2	Honorary Teacher	43	47,62
3	Subject Teacher	45	48,42
Amount		91	100

Source: Primary Data, Respondents(2024)

From Table 5, it can be seen that 3 respondents had the position of principal (3.96%), 43 were honorary teachers (47.62%), and 45 were regular teachers (48.42%). Based on the characteristics of this position level, it is hoped that respondents will still try to improve their work performance by collecting credit scores for functional teacher positions.

A) Inferential Analysis Results

1. Outer model Evaluation(measurement model)

Outer Model is done to see the influence between latent variables and their indicators. The aim is to validate the model and test the reliability of existing constructs, in accordance with theory and empirical studies.

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a. Construct validity test results

Convergent validity

Convergent validity measured using average variance extracted (AVE), and the magnitude is 0.5 or more (Shrestha, 2021). Discriminant validity acceptable if outer loading or Cross –Loading per item construct above 0.70 and average variance extracted (AVE) is 0.50 or more (Hair et al., 2014; Hamid et al., 2017; Hair et al., 2020; and Shrestha, 2021).

Table 6. Discriminant Validity Cross –Loading Validity Test

No	MS	LK	TK	KG
X1.1	0.659			
X1.2	0.768			
X1.3	0.816			
X1.4	0.677			
X2.1		0.821		
X2.2		0.800		
X2.3		0.896		
X2.4		0.854		
Y1.1			0.895	
Y1.2			0.905	
Y1.3			0.823	
Y1.4			0.927	
Y1.5			0.876	
Y2.1				0.835
Y2.2				0.875
Y2.3				0.929
Y2.4				0.898
Y2.5				0.928

Source: Primary data processed in 2024

If the correlation value between a construct and its own indicator is greater than the correlation between the construct and other indicators, it means the construct is latent. Based on this explanation, value of cross-loading of all variables in the block greater than value of cross-loading of other latent variable (Table 5.7).

The validity of the Fornell Larcker Validity Test

To determine construct validity, a validity test is used and can be used Discriminant validity with Average Variant Extracted (AVE), when the minimum value is 0.5 (Hair *et al.*, 2014). Based on test results of discriminant validity, the AVE value of each latent variable correlation is greater than the other latent variables with a minimum value of 0.690.

a. Construct reliability test results

Table 7. Construct Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Social capital	0,9	0,9	0,8
Work environment	0,9	0,9	0,7
Technology	0,7	0,9	0,6
Teacher Performance	0,9	0,9	0,8

Source: Primary data processed in 2024

Meanwhile, the results of the construct reliability test using composite reliability, The results show that all constructs in this study have composite reliability minimum value is 0.7 (Table 5.8) while the composite reliability minimum value is 0.7 so that all constructs in the research have good internal consistency in testing the influence between constructs in the inner model. Reliability test uses average variance extracted (AVE) value, the results show that the lowest AVE value for all constructs is 0.6. This research has an AVE that exceeds the minimum limit required in reliability analysis. So the variables in this study have internal consistency which is good for use in analyzing the influence between variables. All constructs in this research are reliable because they meet the requirements.

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Hypothesis test

Statistical test results of the influence between factors (Estimate for Path Coefficients) is the significance of the path coefficient value which shows the strong influence of the exogenous construct on endogenous development which is completed using the Bootstrap Procedure in the Partial Least Square (PLS) program application. Interaction bootstrap can produce a description of the exploration model as in Figure 8. Results of testing the meaning of the coefficients using the exploration model method

Table 8. Test results Path Coefficient

Variable	Original Sample(O)	Sample Mean (M) (STDEV)	Standard Deviation (O/STDEV)	T-values	p-values	Description
Social Capital □ Teacher Performance	0,056	0,064	0,034	1,633	0,102	Not Significant
Work environment □ Teacher Performance	0,208	0,208	0,075	2,773	0,006	Significant
Technology □ Teacher Performance	0,656	0,651	0,078	8,459	0,000	Significant
Social Capital □ Technology □ Teacher Performance	-0,026	-0,030	0,033	0,790	0,429	Not Significant
Work environment □ Technology □ Teacher Performance	-0,058	-0,054	0,035	1,644	0,100	Not Significant

Source: Author's processed data 2024

Table 8 shows that of the two causal relationships between exogenous variables and endogenous variables, there is one significant relationship (the hypothesis is accepted) at α 0.05 with a statistical value of >1.96 . There are three relationships between exogenous variables and endogenous variables that are significant (hypothesis rejected) at α 0.05 with a statistical value <1.96 .

4.2 DISCUSSION

At this stage, we will explain the discussion of the results of the hypotheses that have been carried out.

1. The influence of social capital on teacher performance among High School/Equivalent School teachers in Cendi Manik Village, Sekotong District, West Lombok Regency, West Nusa Tenggara.

The results of testing the influence between social capital and teacher performance show that social capital has a positive and insignificant effect. This indicates that social capital cannot be relied on as a trigger for improving teacher performance. The results of this research mean that extensive and close relationship capital cannot improve teacher performance. A wide network does not always mean that teachers get what the teaching objectives are. The results of this research are in line with research conducted by However, social capital has two types of messages for certain groups of people, namely those with strong ties such as family and friends or those with weak ties such as acquaintances directing consumers to post and share teaching pattern messages. It should be noted that both types of messages provide information on the quality of teaching information, services and experiences and can influence instructors' intentions and behavior (Johnson, 2012).

On the research of Subramony's *et al.* (2018), found that extensive social capital has no effect on teaching growth because information cannot be easily mobilized towards learning goals. Kebede (2018) found that a very dense network structure will actually create negative gaps in building performance, so there must be policies that can open these gaps and reduce negative gaps that support the informal sector. Several previous studies are in line with those expressed by Johnson (2012); Collie *et al.* (2012); Kraft *et al.* (2016); Ingersoll *et al.* (2014) has a good and positive influence on improving performance. Apart from that, Simbula et al (2011) explained that social capital can encourage students' interest in learning through online/digital media in Taiwan. Mishra (2020) researched 120 teachers in Japan to prove that social capital has a positive effect on learning intentions. Sibieta's (2018) research in New York, Los Angeles, and Chicago found that social capital as measured by usefulness, credibility, information quality, and professionalism effectively predicted the level of learning intention. Structural relationships in social capital are not able to create the same interpretation between teachers in Lombok, West Nusa Tenggara. A very close social capital structure tends to create gaps in supporting teacher performance in teaching, monopolizing certain parties or groups in improving abilities. Resources are not spread evenly, only certain parties' benefit so that the goal of self-innovation is not achieved, creativity is not achieved, and teacher performance in this case is also not achieved.

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The relationship between teachers, as well as very broad, dense groups that have the same interpretation or interpretation is an application of social capital theory but does not become a driver for improving teacher performance. Density in the network makes information dissemination uneven and different interpretations emerge, giving rise to a sense of competition.

2. The influence of the work environment on teacher performance among High School/Equivalent School teachers in Cendi Manik Village, Sekotong District, West Lombok Regency, West Nusa Tenggara.

The results of testing the influence of the work environment on teacher performance show that the work environment has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance. This gives an indication that the work environment really helps teachers in acquiring knowledge and information that supports the teaching they carry out. The work environment has a role in exchanging information and knowledge that is useful in teaching, especially in areas/villages that are still developing.

A supportive work environment can support teacher productivity in their work, including; the existence of adequate teaching facilities, lighting, privacy of the work space, cleanliness, color selection, safety, good size and layout of the work space, and relationships between co-workers and superiors are important things to pay attention to in creating a pleasant working atmosphere. This research is in line with research (Alamry, 2022) where in its findings, the internal and external environment creates a situation where a teaching staff feels comfortable and enjoys their workplace. Likewise with Alamry's (2022) findings, the work environment in schools must be able to support the work of teachers so that they can work well, comfortably and conductively, so that high performance will result.

Almost all work environments at High School at Lombok, West Nusa Tenggara have supporting facilities, so that exchanging information becomes easier. The teachers teach with closeness to the students, so that learning can pass from teacher to student.

3. The role of technology in moderating the influence of social capital on teacher performance among High School/Equivalent School teachers in Cendi Manik Village, Sekotong District, West Lombok Regency, West Nusa Tenggara.

This research finds that technology moderates the influence of social capital on teacher performance. These findings indicate that social capital from Social Capital theory does not fully have a big influence on learning innovation in the form of technological support, there needs to be supporting facilities and infrastructure. Apart from that, technology for areas that are still in villages, internet connection is a special concern, there are few providers and demographic location is also another factor. Learning can be done using online media such as Zoom and strong networks in villages such as families that are still close are not able to encourage this because the actors (teachers) still have to increase their knowledge.

So this research is not in line with previous research by (Putrid an Imaniyati, 2017) that technology has a positive impact on education such as the exchange of information needed by students will be faster because it is easy to access for educational purposes. This is also not in line with research (Liang and Akiba, 2017; Hughes, 2014), which states that innovation in learning is increasingly developing with e-learning innovation which makes the educational process easier, advances in information technology. By utilizing information technology, teachers can present more interesting material.

The role of technology in moderating the influence of the work environment on the performance of High School/Equivalent School teachers in Cendi Manik Village, Sekotong District, West Lombok Regency, West Nusa Tenggara.

This research found that technology pseudo-moderates the work environment on teacher performance. Technology is a pseudo moderation between the work environment and performance so that hypothesis H4 is rejected. The use of technology, for example in searching for material via Google, making presentations and learning videos, cannot be maximized due to the network from the West Lombok, West Nusa Tenggara area. The work environment here means the abilities of teachers, technology tends to have to be supported by the abilities of teachers so that there is a need for training in new technological facilities. So this research is not in line with previous research conducted by (Zeichner, 2014) which obtained results that there was an influence of technology on the relationship between the work environment and teacher performance through educational delivery technology that can be used as a learning development. Research (Simon & Johnson, 2015) conducted on education in China shows that technology accelerates learning so that the work environment becomes more productive.

5. RESEARCH CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

5.1 Conclusion

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion of research results, it can be concluded as follows:

- 1) Social capital is proven to have no significant effect on teacher performance. This means that a wide and dense network of relationships does not have an effect on improving teacher performance for high school/vocational school level teachers in Cendi Manik Village, Sekotong District, West Lombok Regency, West Nusa Tenggara.

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- 2) The work environment has been proven to have a significant positive effect on teacher performance. This means that the better the work environment, the better the teacher performance will be at the High School/Equivalent School teachers in Cendi Manik Village, Sekotong District, West Lombok Regency, West Nusa Tenggara.
- 3) Technology is not proven to moderate social capital on teacher performance. This means that technology must be balanced with other things to support it, for example balancing knowledge with training and updating the knowledge of the teachers themselves at high school/vocational school level teachers in Cendi Manik Village, Sekotong District, West Lombok Regency, West Nusa Tenggara.
- 4) Technology is not proven to moderate the work environment on teacher performance. This means that technology must be balanced with a good working environment, and other things, for example improving the supporting environment such as networks and knowledge for high school/vocational school level teachers in Cendi Manik Village, Sekotong District, West Lombok Regency, West Nusa Tenggara.

5.2 Suggestions

Based on the limitations of the research described above, there are suggestions that will be made so that they are useful for future research, namely: For researchers, if they are going to conduct similar research, it is best to make improvements to the questionnaire, so that the reliability and validity figures can be better. It is hoped that in future research, other variables will be added that can influence teacher performance or become other variables, to answer the phenomena that occurred in this research. The number of respondents is greater and from various positions from the lowest employees to management elements, so that more samples are obtained, the results of the research analysis will be more accurate.

6. RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS

The results of this research are used as input for teachers and related agencies in carrying out their duties and responsibilities for work, creating a conducive work environment in order to create commitment among teachers to improve the quality of education.

Shared interpretation and hope to be mutually reliable, foster a sense of mutual trust to move forward between fellow teachers. A conducive environment such as teacher knowledge can be obtained in workshops related to teaching design and gaining knowledge from seminars about the teaching and learning process, as well as always maintaining good relationships with students and other environments such as the family are very important in improving the performance of high school/vocational school teachers in Cendi Manik Village, Sekotong District, West Lombok Regency, West Nusa Tenggara.

REFERENCES

- 1) Ahmad, Y., Tewal, B., & Taroreh, R. N. (2019). The Influence of Work Stress, Workload, and Work Environment on Employee Performance at Pt. Fif Group Manado. *EMBA Journal: Journal of Economic, Management, Civil Service and Accounting Research*, 7(3).
- 2) Alhadabi, A., & Karpinski, A. C. (2020). Grit, self-efficacy, achievement orientation goals, and academic performance in University students. *International Journal of Adolescence and Youth*, 25(1), 519-535.
- 3) Abdullah, A. (2020). Relationship the Work Culture and Training Programs Within Performance. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies (IJPSAT)*, 20(1), 92-101.
- 4) Ali, H. (2022). Literature Review the Effect of Division of Work and Workload on Work Effectiveness and its Impact on Employee Performance. *Dinasti International Journal of Economics, Finance & Accounting*, 3(2), 227-240.
- 5) Andriani, S., Kesumawati, N., & Kristiawan, M. (2018). The influence of the transformational leadership and work motivation on teachers performance. *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*, 7(7), 19-29.
- 6) Andriani, S., Kesumawati, N., & Kristiawan, M. (2018). The influence of the transformational leadership and work motivation on teachers performance. *International Journal of Scientific & Technology Research*, 7(7), 19-29.
- 7) Blömeke, S., Houang, R., Hsieh, F. J., & Wang, T. Y. (2017). Effects of job motives, teacher knowledge and school context on beginning teachers' commitment to stay in the profession: A longitudinal study in Germany, Taiwan and the United States. In G. K. LeTendre & M. Akiba (Eds.), *International handbook of teacher quality and policy* (pp. 374–387). London: Routledge.
- 8) Cahyono, A. E., Herawati, Y. W., Anshory, A., & Muntaqim, A. (2022). Online teaching by digital native and digital immigrant lecturers of higher education. *International Journal of Innovative Technologies in Social Science*, 4(36), 1-14.
- 9) Collie, R. J., Shapka, J. D., & Perry, N. E. (2012). School climate and social-emotional learning: Predicting teacher stress, job satisfaction, and teaching efficacy. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 104(4), 1189.

The Role of Technology Use in Moderating the Influence of Social Capital and Work Environment on Teacher Performance

- 10) Dunaetz, D. R. (2022). When Technology Does More Harm than Good: Technostress in Missionary Contexts. *Dunaetz, DR (2022) When technology does more harm than good: Technostress in missionary contexts. Journal of the Evangelical Missiological Society, 2(1), 112-128.*
- 11) Darling-Hammond, L., Hyster, M. E., Gardner, M. (2017). Effective teacher professional development. Palo Alto, CA: Learning Policy Institute.
- 12) Granić, A., & Marangunić, N. (2019). Technology acceptance model in educational context: A systematic literature review. *British Journal of Educational Technology, 50(5), 2572-2593.*
- 13) Hale, T., Angrist, N., Goldszmidt, R., Kira, B., Petherick, A., Phillips, T., ... & Tatlow, H. (2021). A global panel database of pandemic policies (Oxford COVID-19 Government Response Tracker). *Nature human behaviour, 5(4), 529-538.*
- 14) Hancock, P. A., & Matthews, G. (2019). Workload and performance: Associations, insensitivities, and dissociations. *Human factors, 61(3), 374-392.*
- 15) Hughes, K. 2014. Work/place' Media. *Media, Culture & Society 36 (5): 644–660.*
- 16) Hayat, A. A., Shateri, K., Amini, M., & Shokrpour, N. (2020). Relationships between academic self-efficacy, learning-related emotions, and metacognitive learning strategies with academic performance in medical students: a structural equation model. *BMC medical education, 20(1), 1-11.*
- 17) Hair, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., Anderson, R. E., & Tatham, R. L. (2006). *Multivariate data analysis 6th Edition.*
- 18) Hermawan, E., Komala, M., & Yohana, C. (2020). THE IMPACT OF WORK LOAD AND WORK STRESS ON EMPLOYEE ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENTS MOBILE SAKTI COMPANY. *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology, 17(6), 5787-5802.*
- 19) Heidari, A., Navimipour, N. J., & Unal, M. (2022). Applications of ML/DL in the management of smart cities and societies based on new trends in information technologies: A systematic literature review. *Sustainable Cities and Society, 104089.*
- 20) Ingersoll, R., Merrill, L., & May, H. (2014). What are the effects of teacher education and preparation on beginning teacher attrition?. Philadelphia: Consortium for Policy Research in Education, University of Pennsylvania.
- 21) Ingersoll, R. (2017). Misdiagnosing America's teacher quality problem. In G. K. LeTendre & M. Akiba (Eds.), *International handbook of teacher quality and policy* (pp. 79–96). London: Routledge.
- 22) Jaiswal, A., Sengupta, S., Panda, M., Heart, L., Priksat, V., Patel, P. and Mohyuddin, S. (2022). Teleworking: role of psychological well-being and technostress in the relationship between trust in management and employee performance, *International Journal of Manpower*, Vol. ahead-of-print No. ahead-of-print. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJM-04-2022-0149>
- 23) Johnson, S. M., Kraft, M. A., & Papay, J. P. (2012). How context matters in high-need schools: The effects of teachers' working conditions on their professional satisfaction and their students' achievement. *Teachers College Record, 114(10), 1–39.*
- 24) Kuchai, O., Skyba, K., Demchenko, A., Savchenko, N., Necheporuk, Y., & Rezvan, O. (2022). The Importance of Multimedia Education in the Informatization of Society. *IJCSNS, 797.*
- 25) Kraft, M. A., Marinell, W. H., & Shen-Wei Yee, D. (2016). School organizational contexts, teacher turnover, and student achievement: Evidence from panel data. *American Educational Research Journal, 53(5), 1411–1449.*
- 26) Kunter, M., Klusmann, U., Baumert, J., Richter, D., Voss, T., & Hachfeld, A. (2013). Professional competence of teachers: Effects on instructional quality and student development. *Journal of Educational Psychology, 105(3), 805.*
- 27) Lundahl, L. (2016). Equality, inclusion and marketization of Nordic education: Introductory notes. *Research in Comparative and International Education, 11(1), 3–12.*
- 28) Ljungholm, D. P. (2018). Employee-employer relationships in the gig economy: Harmonizing and consolidating labor regulations and safety nets. *contemp. Readings L. & Soc. Just., 10, 144.*
- 29) Latan and Ghazali, I., H. 2019. *Partial Least Square Concepts, Techniques and Applications Using the Smart PLS 3.0 Program*. Semarang: Diponegoro University Semarang.
- 30) Lindqvist, P., Nordänger, U. K., & Carlsson, R. (2014). Teacher attrition the first five years—A multifaceted image. *Teaching and Teacher Education, 40, 94–103.*
- 31) Lacerenza, C. N., Marlow, S. L., Tannenbaum, S. I., & Salas, E. (2018). Team development interventions: Evidence-based approaches for improving teamwork. *American psychologist, 73(4), 517.*
- 32) Liang, G., & Akiba, M. (2017). Teachers' working conditions: A cross-national analysis using the OECD TALIS and PISA data. In G. K. LeTendre & M. Akiba (Eds.), *International handbook of teacher quality and policy* (pp. 388–402). London: Routledge
- 33) Lukito, L. H., & Alriani, I. M. (2019). The influence of workload, work environment, work stress on employee performance at PT. Sinarmas distribution archipelago Semarang. *Journal of Management Accounting Economics, 25(45).*
- 34) Mallaboyev, N. M., Sharifjanovna, Q. M., & Nodirbek, M. (2022, May). INTERACTION BETWEEN INFORMATION COMPLEXES IN ECONOMIC SPHERES. In *Conference Zone* (pp. 250-253).

The Role of Technology Use in Moderating the Influence of Social Capital and Work Environment on Teacher Performance

- 35) Mishra, S. (2020). Social networks, social capital, social support and academic success in higher education: A systematic review with a special focus on 'underrepresented' students. *Educational Research Review*, 29, 100307.
- 36) Markova, O., Semerikov, S., Striuk, A., Shalatska, H., Nechypurenko, P., & Tron, V. (2019). Implementation of cloud service models in training of future information technology specialists.
- 37) Nabawi, R. (2020). The influence of the work environment, job satisfaction and workload on employee performance. *Maneggio: Master of Management Scientific Journal*, 2(2), 170-183.
- 38) Nugroho, W., & Suroho, A. (2018). Reconstruction of Development Law in Environmental and Natural Resources Regulatory Policy. *Indonesian Environmental Law Journal*, 4(2), 77-110.
- 39) Norawati, S., Zulher, Z., Yunita, A., & Ilyas, I. (2022). Analysis of Compensation and Workload and Its Impact on the Performance of Medical Employees at Bangkinang Regional Hospital. *Journal of Employee and Management Applications (JABM)*, 8(2), 553-553.
- 40) Obamiro, J. K., & Kumolu-Johnson, B. O. (2019). Work environment and employees' performance: Empirical evidence of Nigerian Beverage Firm. *Journal of the Danube University. Economic*, 15(3).
- 41) Park, S., Choi, G. J., & Ko, H. (2020). Information technology-based tracing strategy in response to COVID-19 in South Korea—privacy controversies. *People*, 323(21), 2129-2130.
- 42) Putra, A. A., & Laily, N. (2019). The Influence of Workload, Work Environment and Motivation on Employee Performance at PT Para Bathara Surya. *Journal of Management Science and Research (JIRM)*, 8(9).
- 43) Putri, T. T., Sitepu, I. Y., Sihombing, M., & Silvi, S. (2019). Analysis and detection of hoax contents in Indonesian news based on machine learning. *Journal of Informatics Pelita Nusantara*, 4(1).
- 44) Rawas, S., Zekri, A., & El-Zaart, A. (2022). LECC: Location, energy, carbon and cost-aware VM placement model in geodistributed DCs. *Sustainable Computing: Informatics and Systems*, 33, 100649.
- 45) Ronfeldt, M., Loeb, S., & Wyckoff, J. (2013). How teacher turnover harms student achievement. *American Educational Research Journal*, 50(1), 4–36.
- 46) Saputra, R. W., & Hayaty, R. (2022). The Effect of Discipline and Workload on Employee Performance with Motivation Mediation on Administrative Bureau Employees Leading of the Regional Secretariat of South Kalimantan Province. *East Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 1(6), 1077-1100.
- 47) Setini, M., Yasa, N. N. K., Supartha, I. W. G., Giantari, I. G. A. K., & Rajiani, I. (2020). The passway of women entrepreneurship: Starting from social capital with open innovation, through to knowledge sharing and innovative performance. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 6(2), 25.
- 48) Sapta, I. K. S., Landra, N., Supartha, I. W. G., Asih, D., & Setini, M. (2020). Public health welfare in digital-based resources transformation from social capital and information sharing: Creative industries from village. *Systematic Reviews in Pharmacy*, 11(6), 688-696.
- 49) Setini, M., Yasa, N. N. K. Y., Supartha, I., & Giantari, I. G. A. K. (2021). The effects of knowledge sharing, social capital and innovation on marketing performance. *International Journal of Data and Network Science*, 5(3), 257-266.
- 50) Wang, Z. (2022). Aesthetic evaluation of multidimensional graphic design based on voice perception model and internet of things. *International Journal of System Assurance Engineering and Management*, 13(3), 1485-1496.